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APPLIED RESEARCH

Toward Sustainable Data Collection Processes for Autonomous Vehicles

KOSMAS TSIAKAS^{ID 1,2}, **MAURO BELLONE**^{ID 3,4}, (Member, IEEE), **IOANNIS MARIOLIS**^{ID 1}, **ANTONIOS GASTERATOS**^{ID 2}, (Senior Member, IEEE), **DIMITRIOS TZOVARAS**^{ID 1}, (Senior Member, IEEE), AND **DIMITRIOS GIAKOUIMIS**^{ID 1}

¹Centre for Research and Technology Hellas, Information Technologies Institute, 57001 Thessaloniki, Greece

²Department of Production and Management Engineering, Democritus University of Thrace, 67100 Xanthi, Greece

³FinEst Centre for Smart Cities, Tallinn University of Technology, 19086 Tallinn, Estonia

⁴Universitas Mercatorum, 00186 Rome, Italy

Corresponding author: Kosmas Tsiakas (ktsiakas@iti.gr)

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ABSTRACT The rapid growth of data-driven models in advanced driver assistance systems (ADAS) has been significantly accelerated by the widespread availability of large-scale public datasets enabling more accurate training and benchmarking. Despite this progress, achieving higher autonomy still requires continuous progress in core functionalities, necessitating an increasing supply of high-quality data. This escalating demand, coupled with the growing number of smart vehicles, presents substantial challenges to the sustainability of data operations, particularly concerning computational and energy resource consumption. This paper directly addresses the critical needs for sustainable practices in autonomous vehicle data operations, with a particular focus on data creation and post-processing. To this end, we present an applied study demonstrating a structured integration of existing data handling techniques into a scalable and modular pipeline, that strategically combines existing, proven data management techniques—such as deduplication, compression, anonymization, and event-driven filtering. This pipeline is particularly designed to minimize storage needs and increase data usability, thereby contributing significantly to overarching sustainability objectives without compromising data quality. The practical benefit of the proposed method lies in its ability to reduce storage requirements by over 50%, lower computational overhead, and simplify AI model training workflows using more compact and privacy-compliant datasets. The proposed pipeline has been validated on two real-world autonomous driving datasets, confirming its effectiveness in improving sustainability and efficiency in data operations for autonomous vehicles.

INDEX TERMS Autonomous vehicles, data collection, data processing, green computing, sustainable development.

I. INTRODUCTION

Automated driving technologies and advanced driver assistance systems (AD/ADAS) have shown remarkable progress over the past decade, enabling the development of efficient transportation systems [1] and simultaneously reducing traffic-related incidents [2]. This is directly associated with the increased availability of large-scale and publicly available datasets recorded from multiple geographical regions under

various environmental conditions and with different sensor modalities [3]. Highly influential datasets, such as KITTI [4], cityscapes [5], nuScenes [6] and more, have greatly advanced AI methods that are vital for the operation of smart and autonomous vehicles. However, the transition of vehicles to a higher level of autonomy, capable of operating in unknown regions and less-disciplined traffic situations, is far from a reality [7].

Further advancements in core vehicle functionalities, such as environmental perception [8], [9], trajectory prediction [10], path planning, and localization, are required to

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enable their operation in all weather conditions [11] for structured and unstructured environments [12], potentially leading to the provision of helpful services, such as last mile delivery [13]. Therefore, the need for more large-scale and high-quality data from autonomous vehicles is undeniable [14].

This growing demand for data, along with the constantly increasing number of smart and automated vehicles, poses severe challenges with respect to the sustainability of data operations [15]. The collection, processing, storage and sharing of such large amounts of data leads to significant computational and energy resources. Well-defined sustainability policies, aligned with the various national and international climate-neutral objectives, are therefore essential to guide the entire data lifecycle, and lead to a transport system aligned with the social and cultural sustainability aspects of modern societies [16].

The impact and potential footprint of autonomous vehicles has been extensively studied [17]. Despite this, the significant energy demands associated with onboard data processing in these vehicles have received comparatively less scrutiny. Addressing this gap, research hypothesises that one billion autonomous vehicles, each driving for an hour daily with an 840-watt computer, would consume enough energy to match the emission output of all existing data centers. This underscores the critical importance of adopting sustainable practices across all facets of autonomous vehicle development and deployment.

In this direction, we consider data collection and post-processing critical aspects for autonomous vehicles, which can make a major contribution towards the required sustainability policies. Data collection processes differentiate significantly according to the operating vehicle, the mounted sensors, the environment and the scope of collecting data. However, in all cases, and regardless of the hardware employed, a common post-processing pipeline can be applied in order to reduce redundant storage and improve the accessibility and quality of the recorded data. To this end, it is essential to define a structured and scalable pipeline that is capable to handle the large-scale needs of autonomous vehicles, in terms of data types, size, frequency, and quality. Moreover, this pipeline is designed to align with responsible data stewardship practices by facilitating the production of application-relevant datasets, enforcing baseline privacy protections, and reducing the manual overhead required for data preparation and annotation. In light of the above, our research work focuses on the following research questions:

RQ1 How can sustainability principles be effectively integrated into data collection processes for autonomous vehicles across diverse environments and sensor configurations?

RQ2 What are the design requirements and performance benchmarks for a scalable and modular data post-processing pipeline tailored to autonomous vehicle data?

RQ3 How does structured post-processing impact the quality, privacy compliance, and storage efficiency of datasets collected by autonomous vehicles?

These research questions aim to address the growing need for technically robust and resource-conscious data handling in autonomous vehicle systems. Existing data collection frameworks in this domain typically emphasize raw sensor acquisition, offline labeling, and large-scale data storage, often with limited attention to energy consumption, storage overhead, or long-term environmental impact. For example, while current approaches may support structured data acquisition and post-processing for synchronization and metadata enrichment, they frequently lack explicit mechanisms for optimizing resource usage or minimizing redundant data. In contrast, our proposed pipeline combines and orchestrates a suite of existing tools in a unified workflow that prioritizes data quality, relevance, and resource efficiency. This marks a shift from volume-centric data handling to a lifecycle-aware strategy that integrates selective data acquisition, similarity-based deduplication, on-device anonymization, and compression techniques tailored for edge hardware constraints. By embedding such considerations throughout the pipeline—from data capture to storage—we enable more scalable deployments and reduce the operational and environmental footprint of data collection in autonomous vehicle systems.

By focusing on scalable post-processing solutions and quality-driven data practices, this work seeks to bridge the gap between raw data acquisition and actionable, privacy-conscious insights. The novelty of this work resides not in the creation of new individual algorithms for data management, but in the holistic design, systematic integration, and comprehensive evaluation of an end-to-end pipeline that leverages existing tools to collectively address the multi-faceted problem of data sustainability in autonomous driving. The following contributions outline the practical advancements made in support of these goals.

- 1) A comprehensive definition and practical integration of sustainability principles and best practices within the data collection processes of autonomous vehicles, accounting for diverse operational contexts and sensor configurations.
- 2) The design and implementation of a scalable, modular post-processing pipeline that consolidates existing techniques into a cohesive system for the structured generation of high-quality datasets from heterogeneous sensor data.
- 3) The development and empirical validation of an evaluation framework that emphasizes dataset quality, minimizes redundancy, and optimizes storage efficiency, thereby supporting sustainable data management practices.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section II presents an overview of the related work on data collection and sustainability for autonomous vehicles. Section III

provides a detailed description of the implemented pipeline, while the evaluation and results are presented in Section IV. The discussion of the results is presented in Section V, and Section VI concludes this paper.

II. RELATED WORK

The creation of autonomous driving datasets, which can potentially create a positive impact in the research domain, is a highly complex procedure that requires a substantial number of resources through the entire data creation workflow. This contains at least the following steps:

- Sensor intrinsic & extrinsic calibration [18]
- Data acquisition [19]
- Time synchronization [20]
- Post-processing and analytics extraction [21]
- Data storage and sharing [22]

The development of sustainable data collection frameworks for autonomous driving requires addressing the intersection of three critical domains: computational efficiency, privacy preservation, and environmental sustainability. This convergence creates a complex optimization problem where traditional approaches often prioritize one dimension at the expense of others. To establish a theoretical foundation for our work, we analyze existing literature based on four key evaluation criteria: efficiency, privacy, interoperability, and sustainability.

A. DATA COLLECTION FRAMEWORKS

The fundamental challenge in autonomous driving data collection lies in managing the massive volumes of multi-sensor data while maintaining real-time processing capabilities. Jacob et al. [23] present a scalable and low-cost data collection framework, supporting cameras, LiDAR, IMU and GPS sensors. In this framework, a two-stage pipeline is introduced to minimize the information loss during the real-time capturing of data. The first stage records raw sensor data as binary files written directly to disk and metadata as ROS bag files, while the second stage combines these two into a single ROS bag file as output. Building on top of this work, Lakshminarayana et al. [24] present a holistic framework and infrastructure to capture, evaluate, and maintain large amounts of multi-sensor data. In this case, data are also recorded as ROS bag files, and a post-processing pipeline is used for data extraction, alignment, and analysis. Specifically, it contains analytical processes to validate the coherency of the data, the accurate positioning of the vehicle, the uniformity of the time series, and it also allows for manual inspection of images and point clouds. In [25] a universal toolbox for the calibration and synchronization of camera, LiDAR and RADAR data is presented, along with a cloud server, running a PostgreSQL database, that allows indexing and querying of data. This work aims to assist the object detection and tracking research tasks and provides procedures for data acquisition and processing systems, while

has back-end data processing algorithms to fuse camera, LiDAR and radar. However, the above-mentioned approaches prioritize data integrity over energy efficiency, leading to resource-intensive storage and processing patterns.

The temporal dimension of data processing presents a critical trade-off between real-time responsiveness and computational efficiency. Saaristola et al. [26] address this issue by introducing the division of the overall system into data selection, data extraction, and data transmission, while its design is based on existing legislation and industry standards that affect data recording procedures, supporting interoperability efforts. However, the overall data creation workflow lacks a standardized approach [3] concerning the data attributes, terminology, and structure, as well as labelling and post-processing pipelines. Such guidelines would boost the quality of generated datasets, resulting in enhanced collaboration within the research community.

To this end, it is insightful to study the existing datasets and the publicly available data collection pipelines to identify common steps in the data creation process. In the multi-vehicle data acquisition platform of [27], post-processing refers to the removal of outliers for the object trajectory tracking estimation. From the perspective of privacy and volume minimization, only the Zenseact Open Dataset (ZOD) [28] explicitly describes several post-processing steps for data anonymization and compression. Specifically, ZOD employs third-party services to anonymize human faces and vehicle license plates using both blurring and Deep Neural Anonymization (DNAT) methods. The latter is tackled through JPG compression to reduce the memory footprint, and their work contains an extensive analysis regarding the effects of the anonymization and the compression on the accuracy of the AI models.

From the perspective of data minimization, there is an imperative need to eliminate the continuous and long-term data capturing [24], which leads to enormous amounts of data and affects transfer, accumulation and access to the data. To this end, recent literature contains various approaches for event-based recording [29]. This refers to the storage of specific data recordings, commonly of short duration, based on pre-defined triggering mechanisms [30], such as the sudden vehicle deceleration, specific behaviors of surrounding vehicles and pedestrians, and the identification of traffic incidents. This is also fully aligned with a core principle of GDPR – the data minimization. This means that organizations should only collect, process, and retain the minimum amount of personal data that is strictly necessary to achieve a specific, explicit, and legitimate purpose, rather than indiscriminately collecting and storing all available data. The selective recording paradigm presents opportunities for sustainable data collection but requires intelligent filtering mechanisms that can balance data utility with resource consumption. Current approaches lack systematic frameworks for evaluating the environmental cost-benefit ratio of different data collection strategies.

B. SUSTAINABLE DATA MANAGEMENT POLICIES

The urge for impactful climate policies directly affects multiple domains, including energy, transport, mobility, and industry, while critical enablers towards these policies are edge computing, IoT, and AI [31]. Data are also a core component to lead the transition for greener policies since they are capable of providing critical insights into environmental conditions, energy consumption patterns, and resource usage [32]. Overall, the effective utilization of data can lead to the creation of more sustainable solutions.

Even though a stand-alone definition for *Green Data* does not yet exist, the European Green Deal [33] provides various policies and initiatives that encompass two main directions: 1) high-quality, curated data that improve sustainability and energy efficiency and; 2) data processed, stored, and managed in an environmentally sustainable manner through eco-friendly infrastructure [34]. These policies are part of the European data strategy [35], which aims to establish a single data market, ensure seamless data flow, and promote sustainability. The scientific community approaches the topic of *Green Data* also from multiple aspects, all centered on the creation of technical solutions to create more sustainable AI solutions [36], [37] and the use of AI towards the transition to a sustainable circular economy [38], [39].

While both the EU and the scientific community share the overarching goal of environmental sustainability through digital means, their interpretations of “green data” differ primarily in their scope and operational focus. The EU sets the strategic direction and creates the demand for green solutions, while the research community provides the foundational scientific understanding and the technological means to achieve those goals.

In the modern data-driven societies, it is essential to clearly define green and sustainable practices, which can be applied during the data creation process, and can have a positive impact towards the EU goals. In this context, green data refers to data that is collected, processed, stored, and utilized in ways that minimize environmental impact throughout its entire lifecycle [40].

This encompasses reducing energy consumption, optimizing resource usage, and mitigating carbon emissions associated with data operations. This holistic view aligns with principles of the circular economy applied to data, advocating for strategies such as data minimization, extended data reuse, and effective data disposal to reduce waste and maximize resource efficiency throughout the data lifecycle [41]. Once these practices are defined, technical guidelines and policies can be adopted by the involved stakeholders and provide direct benefits to everyone.

In order to define these practices, it is essential to investigate existing approaches towards the greener data creation. Existing approaches often focus on optimizing data post-collection or within infrastructure [42], rather than minimizing the environmental footprint from the initial acquisition [43], processing at the edge, and subsequent management throughout its lifecycle. This oversight leads

to unnecessary energy consumption from data transmission, redundant storage, and inefficient cloud-based processing pipelines.

On the ecosystem of data spaces, MobiSpaces [44] optimizes processing at the edge, thus reducing energy consumption of data-intensive operations that typically run in the cloud. It also contains an intelligent resource-allocation mechanism, which takes into account the energy consumption in order to prioritize tasks. This approach paves the direction towards more efficient practices of data spaces.

Beyond specific project implementations like MobiSpaces, the European Union is actively fostering the creation of Common European Data Spaces, with a strong emphasis on sustainability. A prime example is the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS), a key pillar of the European Green Deal [45]. The GDDS aims to facilitate the secure and trusted sharing of vast amounts of environmental data across sectors – including climate change, biodiversity, zero pollution, and circular economy – to enable evidence-based policymaking and foster innovative green solutions. This initiative highlights the strategic importance of organized data sharing and interoperability in achieving ambitious environmental goals.

Furthering these efforts, several other EU-funded initiatives are actively developing components for a more sustainable data ecosystem. For instance, projects like SAGE (The Data Space for a Sustainable Green Europe) aim to establish fully operational Green Deal Data Spaces to improve accessibility and integration of ecological and environmental data. Similarly, AD4GD (All Data for Green Deal) focuses on co-creating open, FAIR data hubs to support key Green Deal priorities, demonstrating a concerted push towards leveraging data spaces for comprehensive environmental action [46].

C. GAP ANALYSIS AND POSITIONING

Following the analysis above, it becomes obvious that the current literature treats sustainability as an auxiliary concern, rather than a core design principle. As shown in Table 1, existing works take into account data compression [28], edge computing [44] and data minimization [19], however, no existing framework provides a holistic integration of sustainability objectives within the entire data lifecycle. Also, privacy is not widely embodied in current data collection frameworks or public datasets, even though the need for compliant data and algorithms has widely increased. The overall lack of sustainable objectives is also relevant to the absence of clear and measurable metrics, which can be used to measure the impact of the generated datasets and the algorithms through a standardized method. Based on this analysis, our work aims to provide a comprehensive pipeline that is based on privacy-by-design and sustainability-by-design principles, suitable for multi-modal sensorized vehicles and edge-based deployment.

TABLE 1. Comparative positioning of existing methods in terms of data compression, privacy, interoperability and edge processing.

Framework	Compression	Privacy	Interoperability	Edge processing
[23]	✗	✗	✗	✓
[24]	✗	✗	✓	✗
[26]	✓	✓	✓	✓
[25]	✗	✗	✓	✗
[28]	✓	✓	✗	✗
[44]	✗	✗	✓	✓
Ours	✓	✓	✓	✓

III. METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

As can be seen from the analysis above, green and sustainable practices have been considered for higher-level usage of data and for the infrastructure used. However, there is no direct guideline towards the greener data creation of data, which aims to reduce the environmental footprint from the very first moment of data collection, reducing also the overhead for data transmission and cloud-based pipelines, where processing usually happens. In this context, the concept of green data should not be perceived as an abstract environmental ideal, but rather as a practical and economic necessity. By minimizing unnecessary data collection and optimizing data structures from the outset, energy consumption associated with data transmission, storage, and processing can be significantly reduced. This not only contributes to environmental sustainability, but also leads to tangible benefits such as lower operational costs and improved system performance, as data retrieval and analysis become faster and more efficient.

The proposed work serves as a core component of an EU-funded project, PLIADES,¹ which aims to integrate AI technologies into the entire data lifecycle, starting from data creation up to the data sharing and usage, with the overall aim to improve data quality and boost interoperability among various domains, including autonomous driving. For the specific scenarios of autonomous vehicles, greener data creation will refer to a set of best practices aimed at minimizing environmental footprint and enhancing data efficiency:

- **Collect essential data:** Prioritizing the collection of the minimum essential data is a critical best practice to minimize energy during transmission, storage requirements, and data management. Essential data generally refers to data that are critical and necessary for a specific purpose, function, or process.
- **Store essential data:** The adoption of data de-duplication techniques to reduce redundancy and optimize storage capacity.
- **Use energy efficient processing:** Utilizing energy-efficient data processing pipelines, preferably executed at the edge, to limit reliance on energy-intensive cloud infrastructure.

- **Reduce digital garbage:** Establishing clear data life-cycle management policies, including timely disposal and deletion of obsolete or unused data, to prevent unnecessary storage overhead.
- **Use index friendly formatting:** Structuring datasets to support efficient indexing and downstream processing, which reduces computational load and accelerates data retrieval operations.

The preceding state-of-the-art analysis highlights a critical gap in existing research: the insufficient consideration of environmental sustainability in autonomous vehicle data operations. Building upon this, the proposed work introduces clear guidelines and details the systematic integration and application of established data processing techniques into a comprehensive, customizable pipeline specifically designed to reduce the environmental footprint of these data processes. Unlike previous studies that often overlook data sustainability, our paper explicitly addresses this oversight by identifying actionable policies and suggesting specific, modular components to achieve these goals. This versatile pipeline is uniquely designed to accommodate diverse data collection scenarios and can be precisely tailored to meet the specific requirements and objectives of any data acquisition session, thereby providing a significant step towards sustainable autonomous driving.

A. DATA PROCESSING PIPELINE

The studied methodology adopts a scalable and modular architecture, depicted in Fig. 1. It is designed for scenarios where an autonomous vehicle has already completed a data collection operation, and the recorded data are stored locally in the form of ROS bag files. As highlighted in the previous related work analysis, ROS bags remain the most prominent way for recording multi-sensor data for smart vehicles. For this reason, they are selected as the primary input for our pipeline. The raw ROS messages are subsequently transformed into a structured file hierarchy, facilitating efficient indexing and enabling the orderly execution of post-processing steps, each of which is explicitly defined in advance. While each of the proposed components may support multiple implementation options, the following sections detail the configurations deemed most optimal for each respective stage. This structured approach not only streamlines data access and transformation, but also establishes a consistent foundation for further analysis, labeling,

¹<https://www.pliades-project.eu/>

TABLE 2. The ROS message types supported by the ROS bag conversion module and their corresponding output file format.

Data Type	ROS Message Type	Format
Point Cloud	sensor_msgs/PointCloud2	.bin
Image (raw)	sensor_msgs/Image	.jpg
Image (compr.)	sensor_msgs/CompressedImage	.jpg
Camera Info	sensor_msgs/CameraInfo	.json
Lidar Scan	sensor_msgs/LaserScan	.json
IMU	sensor_msgs/Imu	.json
GPS Fix	sensor_msgs/NavSatFix	.json
Odometry	nav_msgs/Odometry	.json

or sharing. The core idea behind this architecture is to support interoperability and flexibility, allowing multiple vehicles to produce data that comply with a unified structure, even with different sensors and vehicle configuration. This promotes a hardware-agnostic data workflow, contributing to more sustainable and reusable data practices. The methodology under investigation serves as a guideline for data collection operations in the autonomous driving domain.

B. ROS BAG CONVERSION

The initial step of the proposed pipeline is the conversion of data from one or multiple ROS bag files into a structured file hierarchy, which allows more efficient indexing, querying, and retrieval of the corresponding data. The extracted file structure is inspired by [24] and is customizable according to the raw data contained in the ROS bag. The extracted data are organized into a hierarchical file structure based on the following metadata structure:

Metadata Structure

Location: <Location>

Date: <Date of recording>

Time: <Time of recording>

Source: <Sensor name>

Timestamp: <Timestamp in Unix time>

Extension: <Extension>

The configuration of this module, which can easily be performed through a YAML file, requires the definition of the source name that is used for naming the corresponding directory, the ROS topic and the ROS message type for each of the contained data sources. The most common and essential ROS messages that need to be converted, according to the publicly available AV datasets, are shown in Table 2, along with the corresponding file format. Each ROS message contains a timestamp in Unix time with nanosecond precision, which eases the synchronization between different modalities. This timestamp is used directly as the filename for each saved frame.

C. IMAGE DEDUPLICATION

Image deduplication involves identifying and removing consecutive image frames that exhibit a high degree of similarity. This process helps reduce storage requirements without compromising the integrity or richness of the

recorded information. During data collection, vehicles often remain stationary or move through environments with minimal variation. In such cases, continuously recording every frame can result in large volumes of redundant data. This redundancy increases the burden of post-processing and annotation, particularly for high-frequency sensors such as vision cameras.

To validate the reliability of autonomous vehicles, extensive driving data—often amounting to billions of miles—is required [47]. However, if the captured scenes lack diversity, the value of this data diminishes, making deduplication a crucial step in optimizing both storage and analytical efficiency.

The underlying functionality of image deduplication is depicted in Fig. 2. Each image frame I_t is passed through the backbone of a convolutional neural network in order to extract a feature vector that encodes the semantic content of the scene encoded in a high-dimensional vector. In our approach, we utilize the MobileNetV2 [48] architecture, due to its increased accuracy, the real-time capabilities and the low processing needs.

The output of the backbone is a feature vector $\mathbf{f}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{1280}$ for frame I_t at time t . To identify and discard redundant frames, we compute the similarity between the feature vectors of consecutive images \mathbf{f}_t and \mathbf{f}_{t+1} . If the similarity exceeds a predefined threshold τ , the frame is considered a duplicate and excluded from further processing. The threshold τ is empirically selected based on the desired trade-off between storage reduction and scene diversity preservation. Its optimal value depends on the similarity metric used, image resolution, and the degree of motion in the scene. In practice, τ can be tuned using a subset of the dataset through visual inspection of frame similarities or pre-analysis of distance distributions.

Several metrics can be used to estimate the similarity between the feature vectors. Below, we suggest the utilization of: 1) euclidean (L2) distance, 2) cosine similarity, 3) FAISS (Facebook AI Similarity Search) library [49], [50], each one having specific pros and cons, which are described in detail. The expected contribution of those methods is common: the reduction of dataset size without the reduction of insightful information.

1) EUCLIDEAN DISTANCE

The euclidean distance between two feature vectors of consecutive images is calculated as follows:

$$d_{L2}(\mathbf{f}_t, \mathbf{f}_{t+1}) = \|\mathbf{f}_t - \mathbf{f}_{t+1}\|_2 = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (f_t^i - f_{t+1}^i)^2} \quad (1)$$

In Eq. 1 the superscript i denotes the i -th component of the feature vector and n is the total number of features (in this case $n = 1280$). If the two vectors are identical, d_{L2} is closer to 0, while there is no upper bound for the distance. This makes the selection of the thresholding value more challenging and needs to be tuned according to the images.

FIGURE 1. The architecture of the proposed pipeline. The pipeline utilizes ROS bag files—recorded during vehicle operations—as input and converts the contained multi-sensor messages into a structured file hierarchy. This structure enables efficient indexing and supports the sequential execution of post-processing modules, such as image filtering, data anonymization, and event-based selection.

FIGURE 2. The core functionality of image deduplication. Each image is transformed into a feature vector using the backbone of MobileNetV2 and consecutive frames are compared to identify their potential similarity. A thresholding process provides the final decision whether to keep or discard a specific frame. In this example, the frames at time t and $t + 2$ are kept, while the in-between frame $t + 1$ is discarded.

2) COSINE SIMILARITY

Cosine similarity between two feature vectors is calculated as follows:

$$S_c(\mathbf{f}_t, \mathbf{f}_{t+1}) = \frac{\mathbf{f}_t \cdot \mathbf{f}_{t+1}}{\|\mathbf{f}_t\|_2 \|\mathbf{f}_{t+1}\|_2} \quad (2)$$

The outcome of this metric is within the range $[-1, 1]$. A value closer to 1 denotes higher similarity, which is the case of interest in this module, making the selection of the threshold a more straightforward process. A clear advantage of the cosine similarity is its robustness to magnitude differences due to the normalization.

3) FACEBOOK AI SIMILARITY SEARCH LIBRARY (FAISS)

The FAISS library [49], [50] enables efficient similarity search and clustering over dense vector representations. FAISS reports a squared Euclidean distance (L2), which avoids the square root. In this case, the distance calculation is

performed as described in Eq. 3.

$$d_{FAISS}^2(\mathbf{f}_t, \mathbf{f}_{t+1}) = \|\mathbf{f}_t - \mathbf{f}_{t+1}\|_2^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n (f_t^i - f_{t+1}^i)^2 \quad (3)$$

Although it provides excellent scalability and performance for large datasets with native GPU support, its use in the case of consecutive frame comparisons introduces unnecessary complexity and overhead. For such temporally local comparisons, direct distance computation (e.g., L2 or cosine similarity) is typically sufficient and more lightweight. However, FAISS excels when comparing a query vector against a large collection of non-consecutive frames, where brute-force approaches become inefficient. In such scenarios, FAISS provides an effective solution for identifying potential duplicates or redundant frames at scale, without being significantly impacted by the size of the database.

D. ANONYMIZATION

Autonomous vehicles operating in public environments are subject to various regulations, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). This makes anonymization a critical component for datasets post-processing. Specifically, it is imperative to respect specific policies regarding the data collected, that will allow their efficient sharing and extended dataset usability with other organizations, respecting the compliance regulations that apply.

This includes at least the anonymization of human faces and license plates that exist in the image frames of the dataset. This process benefits from being executed on the edge, since it reduces further processing steps once the data have been shared.

Face blurring is based on the CenterFace [51], an anchor-free face detection neural network, combined with Gaussian blurring on the detected faces. CenterFace is suitable for edge devices and can achieve high accuracy results in real-time data streaming.

For license plates blurring, the NVIDIA LPDNet [52], based on object detection models, provides high accuracy with real-time capabilities. Specifically, it achieves more than 99% accuracy on the CCPD-Base dataset [53] and 40 frames per second on a Jetson Nano device, making it suitable for real-time operation.

While anonymization is not inherently related to the environmental aspects of data collection, it contributes indirectly to more resource-efficient practices. By integrating anonymization mechanisms directly into real-time data acquisition pipelines—particularly at the edge—it is possible to produce privacy-compliant datasets without requiring repeated vehicle deployments or additional offline processing. This reduces redundant data collection efforts and minimizes computational overhead in post-processing stages, ultimately lowering energy consumption and operational costs associated with handling sensitive data.

E. EVENT-BASED FILTERING

The most impactful strategy for sustainable data collection is to prevent the collection of redundant data from the beginning. By collecting only the minimum essential data, it significantly reduces the burden on network, processing and storage. Existing AI algorithms for autonomous vehicles fail to identify real-world corner cases, which is a direct consequence of the fact that existing datasets may contain long driving scenes, but their content does not provide enough edge cases and cannot provide significant enhancements for future development.

To address this, we propose an event-based filtering approach that automatically captures raw data only for the cases of interest, such as edge cases, identification of unknown objects, or specific vehicle events that need further investigation. An event in this context refers to a high-level, user-defined semantic occurrence detected within the data stream, which triggers automatic data recording for specific

periods of time. Each event is recorded for a fixed duration both before and after its emergence, ensuring that contextual information is preserved for analysis.

Our pipeline consists of a series of events that enable automated data capturing. Each of these events can be activated or deactivated according to the scope of the data collection operation. These events are the following:

- **People detection in the scene:** The presence of pedestrians or other individuals in the vehicle's environment is a critical safety consideration and a frequent source of complex interactions.
- **Sudden braking of the vehicle:** Abrupt deceleration often indicates a critical situation, such as an emergency stop, an unexpected obstacle, or a near-collision, providing valuable data for understanding hazardous scenarios.

For the identification of people in the scene, we utilize the YOLO11 [54] object detector, due to its proven real-time inference capabilities and its relatively high accuracy in edge devices. The detection of sudden braking events is achieved through the analysis of the vehicle's onboard IMU sensor. Abrupt changes in its acceleration and angular velocity measurements are straightforward to identify, compared to the normal smooth operation of a vehicle. These deviations of expected motion profiles reliably indicate a significant event for recording of a critical occurrence that potentially provides insightful data for further investigation.

However, the above-mentioned events do not comprehensively capture the wide range of edge cases that occur in real-world driving scenarios. Examples include abnormal lane changes, traffic light malfunctions, animals crossing, partially occluded traffic signs, and reflective surfaces, among others. The current absence of datasets containing such events prevents the development of corresponding identification models. This limitation, however, highlights an opportunity for organizations and industrial partners with the necessary resources to capture and reproduce these complex scenarios in future work.

F. DATA COMPRESSION

The final step of our proposed data collection pipeline is the efficient sampling and compression of the captured data. Effective compression strategies are essential to minimize long-term storage requirements and reduce network bandwidth consumption. The type of compression is tightly coupled with the data type and format, with varying trade-offs between compression ratio and computational overhead.

Regarding image data, which often constitute the most storage-demanding data generated by autonomous vehicles, the JPEG format [55] employs a lossy compression algorithm, which decreases image quality according to the desired level of compression. In some cases, this lossy compression might lead to the loss of information or image clarity. In contrast, PNG format provides lossless compression, at the cost of larger file sizes. This requires a quality-size trade-off analysis to balance the needs of storage and data quality.

(a) CERTH autonomous vehicle platform.

(b) Sensor setup used in the ISEAUTO platform.

FIGURE 3. Illustration of two different autonomous vehicle platforms used in the study.

For non-image data, generic metadata and sensor readings, such as LiDAR measurements, IMU and GPS, lossless compression algorithms are preferred to preserve the integrity and precision of numerical data. In our pipeline, we employ the general-purpose compression library *zlib* [56], however these data, which are commonly stored in binary, CSV or JSON files, do not have large storage requirements by default.

IV. EVALUATION

In order to evaluate the efficiency of our proposed pipeline, its contributions to the sustainability of the data generation and the effectiveness of each proposed component, we perform experiments of two different datasets. The first dataset is captured from the autonomous vehicle of CERTH/ITI, which is depicted in Fig. 3a, and is equipped with 4 LiDAR sensors, 1 RGB stereo camera, a GPS and an IMU sensor. The recording was performed in the semi-structured CERTH premises. The second dataset used is *iseAuto* [57], [58], which was captured on the TalTech campus using the vehicle depicted in Fig. 3b.

The primary distinction between the two datasets lies in their format and level of processing. The CERTH dataset

provides raw recorded data in ROS1 format, whereas the *iseAuto* dataset has already undergone extraction and post-processing. In *iseAuto*, only one out of every seven frames from all point clouds and images has been retained. Additionally, the image resolutions differ significantly: CERTH contains images at 1280×720 , while *iseAuto* offers much higher-resolution images at 4240×2824 , thus resulting in a higher computational time. Another key difference is in environmental diversity. *iseAuto* includes scenes captured during nighttime and rainy weather, offering a broader range of driving conditions. In contrast, CERTH is limited to daytime recordings in sunny weather. It should be noted that all proposed components are deterministic, producing identical outputs when executed with the same parameters and input data. Consequently, repeated runs yield identical results.

A. ROS BAG CONVERSION

The statistics of the raw CERTH dataset, initially stored in 78 ROS bag files, are described in Table 3. For each sensor modality, we calculate the initial size it acquires in the disk as a ROS message and the size of the extracted data. From the conversion, it is shown that image and point cloud data reduce their overall storage needs just by their conversion. For images, their conversion was into JPEG format with 100% quality, while the LiDAR data are stored in *.bin* files. In contrast, data from IMU and GPS require low storage, even as ROS messages, however their conversion does not affect the overall data set size significantly and for consistency we convert them into JSON files.

B. IMAGE DEDUPLICATION

The evaluation of this component involves the identification and removal of duplicate frames in both datasets, using all three proposed methods: 1) L2 distance, 2) cosine similarity; and 3) FAISS framework. Table 5 contains the results of the evaluation for different threshold values for both datasets. FAISS is using squared L2 distances, in contrast to the simple L2 distance calculation that we perform. For this reason, we selected the same threshold values but converted into squared distance space.

The evaluation of this component was performed on a CPU and, as can be seen in Table 5, the processing time per frame for the *iseAuto* dataset is considerably higher. This is justified by the increased image size (4240×2824 pixels) compared to the smaller images of CERTH (1280×720 pixels). In the above analysis, it also becomes clear how the selection of the threshold value affects the final number of frames. The purpose of this module is to reduce the number of frames without reducing the quality of information. In Fig. 4 we depict the calculated distances between consecutive frames, combined with an indicative threshold. The diagram proves the clear similarity between the frames and provides an indication of the decision on the threshold value. In contrast, Fig. 5 denotes how the consecutive frames have a smaller correlation between them,

TABLE 3. CERTH dataset statistics.

Sensor	Number of frames	Initial size	Extracted size	Size difference
Front camera (compressed)	2566	1.3 GB	824.88 MB	+506.89 MB
Front 2D laser	7011	48.8 MB	51.20 MB	-2.40 MB
Rear 2D laser	2763	40.4 MB	40.15 MB	+0.25 MB
GPS	2768	914.0 KB	678.97 KB	+0.23 MB
IMU	13529	743.0 B	8.63 MB	-8.63 MB
Front LiDAR	2719	8.0 GB	1.83 GB	+6318.24 MB
Left LiDAR	2725	3.6 GB	621.79 MB	+3064.61 MB
Right LiDAR	2712	3.5 GB	611.40 MB	+2972.60 MB
Top LiDAR	2714	9.6 GB	710.15 MB	+9120.25 MB
Overall size difference				21.47 GB

TABLE 4. IseAuto dataset statistics.

Sensor	Number of frames	Size
Front camera	2400	32.1 GB
Front LiDAR	2400	2.5 GB

TABLE 5. Comparison of the image deduplication on CERTH vs. iseAuto dataset frames. The frame count is 2566 for the CERTH dataset, and 2400 for the iseAuto dataset.

Method	Threshold	Average processing time (sec/frame)		Unique images ratio (%)	
		CERTH	IseAuto	CERTH	IseAuto
d_{L2}	3.0			35.58%	98.87%
	2.5	0.015	0.356	52.37%	99.54%
	2.0			75.28%	99.83%
S_c	0.95			30.24%	97.29%
	0.90	0.013	0.394	11.58%	91.69%
	0.85			6.63%	87.86%
d_{FAISS}	$3 \cdot 10^2$			34.81%	90.30%
	$2.5 \cdot 10^2$	0.014	0.313	52.17%	94.59%
	$2 \cdot 10^2$			75.06%	94.00%

and this is expected due to the sampling that has been applied on the dataset. For both figures, we depict the intermediate threshold among the values evaluated in Table 5, which serves as a representative operating point. The threshold values considered in Table 5 are indicative and reflect a practical trade-off between reducing redundancy and preserving useful visual diversity. These values can be adjusted depending on factors such as camera viewpoint, scene dynamics, and application-specific requirements.

C. DATA ANONYMIZATION

For data anonymization, we performed face blurring using the CenterFace neural network on both the CERTH and iseAuto datasets. We evaluated the performance of the system using object-level metrics, rather than per-frame metrics, and each face was treated as a distinct detection instance. We calculate the standard performance metrics – Precision, Recall, and F1-score – which correspond to the ratio of correctly anonymized faces, incorrectly anonymized regions where no face was present, and the number of missed anonymizations.

TABLE 6. Evaluation of the data anonymization.

Dataset	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Proc. time
CERTH	90.52%	99.28%	94.70%	25.65 ms/frame
iseAuto	99.86%	99.86%	99.86%	293.98 ms/frame

The evaluation is conducted on a per-object basis, is independent of the number of frames, and the results are reported in Table 6. Interestingly, only one false positive and false negative over the total number of frames was experienced in the iseAuto dataset, leading to the same values of the metrics in the corresponding row in Table 6.

The blurring process is more efficient in the iseAuto dataset, compared to the CERTH dataset. This is justified by the higher image quality of the dataset, which provides a clearer depiction of the scene. However, this contrasts with the increased processing time required for each image. This trade-off is expected, as higher-resolution images inherently contain more visual detail, which enhances the effectiveness of processes like blurring but also increases the computational load and processing time required per frame.

For the CERTH dataset, false negatives appeared mainly in far distances, where the face was partially unclear. Regarding false positives, they appeared mostly on the rims of surrounding vehicles or in random regions of the image, as depicted in Fig. 6. The threshold for the CenterFace network has been selected relatively low (0.3), since in these cases, due to the severity of compliance, it is preferred to falsely blur a region, instead of not identifying a face on the image.

D. EVENT-BASED FILTERING

For the event-based filtering, we evaluate the identification of the people detection event for both datasets. For the CERTH dataset, we captured all images frames that humans were detected, along with all the corresponding frames, 5 seconds before and after the event triggering. This duration was selected as an average solution for various types of events, however this can be customized according to the event type and the need for longer or shorter duration of data. This resulted in a smaller dataset of 1200 frames and 2.4GB in

(a) L2 distances on CERTH dataset.

(b) Cosine similarity distances on CERTH dataset.

(c) FAISS similarity distances on CERTH dataset.

FIGURE 4. Distances calculated between consecutive frames. The red dotted line indicates an indicative threshold value. Larger spikes correspond to the onset of new recording sessions and reflect substantial visual differences between consecutive frames.

(a) L2 distances on iseAuto dataset.

(b) Cosine similarity distances on iseAuto dataset.

(c) FAISS distances on iseAuto dataset.

FIGURE 5. Distances calculated between consecutive frames. The red dotted line indicates the selected threshold value. Larger spikes correspond to lower correlation between consecutive frames, which is expected as temporal sub-sampling has already been applied to this dataset.

(a) False detection on vehicle rim.

(b) False detection on random image area.

FIGURE 6. Examples of false positives in the face anonymization process. On the left, CenterFace falsely identifies a vehicle rim; on the right, it flags a random non-face region.

total, which is suitable for tasks that involve human presence in the scene.

For the iseAuto dataset, since the data do not contain the timestamp of each frame, it is impossible to isolate the data in before and after the event triggering. For this reason, we extract only the data that contain the presence of human on the images, resulting in a dataset of 304 image and LiDAR frames of 3.5 GB in total. This indicates the necessity to encode the timestamp of each frame recorded, so that it can be utilized in time-sensitive events.

E. COMPRESSION

For the evaluation of the compression component, we examine the compression of image and non-image data (.bin and .json files) separately. As raw frames we consider the lossless PNG images, while the compressed images are JPEG with the highest quality available, so that we eliminate the quality reduction. For non-image data, we compare their initial size and the compressed files using the zlib library. Table 7 contains the results of the comparison for both datasets and the compression rate calculated using Eq. 4.

$$\text{Compression Ratio} = \left(1 - \frac{\text{Compressed Size}}{\text{Original Size}} \right) \times 100\% \tag{4}$$

TABLE 7. Results of the data compression.

Dataset	Image		Non-image		All data
	Raw	Compr.	Raw	Compr.	Ratio
CERTH	2.8 GB	865.0 MB	4.2 GB	2.6 GB	50.8%
iseAuto	32.1 GB	8.1 GB	2.5 GB	1.9 GB	70.9%

For image data, in order to understand the trade-off between storage savings and information retention, we evaluate different compression techniques. Specifically, we compare: 1) PNG, which preserves full pixel fidelity, but results in high storage usage, and 2) various quality levels of JPEG — 100 (nearly lossless), 85 (balanced), and 65 (aggressive compression). For both datasets, we evaluate the compression ratio and the reconstruction Fidelity via PSNR and SSIM scores. Table 8 presents the results of this analysis, which demonstrate a clear trade-off between compression ratio and reconstruction fidelity. For both datasets, JPEG at quality 100 achieves a significant reduction in size (69–75%) with negligible degradation, as evidenced by SSIM values above 0.99 and PSNR exceeding 53 dB. At quality 85, compression ratios exceed 88% for CERTH and 91% for iseAuto, while maintaining high fidelity (SSIM > 0.98, PSNR ~47 dB), making it a practical default for most downstream perception tasks. Aggressive compression at quality 65 pushes storage reduction beyond 90%, but introduces visible artifacts and a measurable drop in fidelity (SSIM ~0.94, PSNR ~40 dB), which may affect tasks sensitive to texture or fine edges. These results suggest that JPEG at quality 85 offers a favorable balance between storage efficiency and data usability, especially in resource-constrained deployments.

TABLE 8. Image fidelity across JPEG quality levels.

Dataset	Quality	Size (MB)	Compression Ratio	PSNR (dB)	SSIM
CERTH	PNG	2800	-	-	-
	JPEG 100	865.0	69.11%	56.25	0.9992
	JPEG 85	330.3	88.21%	47.62	0.9943
	JPEG 65	270.1	90.68%	39.83	0.9743
iseAuto	PNG	32100	-	-	-
	JPEG 100	8100	74.77%	53.00	0.9961
	JPEG 85	2800	91.28%	48.06	0.9893
	JPEG 65	2100	93.46%	40.30	0.9475

F. ABLATION STUDY

The evaluation performed above showcased the capabilities to reduce the required storage needs. However, it is imperative to assess whether the resulting datasets retain functional utility for AI tasks, such as image segmentation. To this end, we validate the suitability of the post-processed data for the task of vehicle and person semantic segmentation on the iseAuto dataset using a CNN-based architecture, YOLO11 [54], and a transformer-based architecture, SegFormer [59]. The experiments were performed solely on this dataset

due to the lack of annotations on the CERTH dataset. Table 9 summarizes the outcomes of this evaluation. For each case, we calculate the mAP50 for the segmentation of people and vehicles separately. We reserved 10% of the dataset samples as a validation set (240 images), maintaining them in their original PNG format without any modifications or post-processing, to ensure fair comparison. The remaining 90% constitutes the training set, and undergoes different preprocessing pipelines depending on whether deduplication, anonymization, and compression components are applied. The experiments were performed using an NVIDIA RTX 3090 GPU. In the experiments where both compression and deduplication are applied, image compression is performed first, followed by deduplication. This ordering explains the slight variations in the number of images, even when using the same deduplication method.

The baseline configuration—without deduplication, anonymization, or compression—achieves strong performance across tasks, with YOLO11 reaching mAP50 values above 86% for person detection and above 90% for car detection, while SegFormer attains IoU scores around 67% for persons and 80% for cars. Introducing anonymization results in a modest performance decrease, most notably for the person class, which is expected since image blurring alters fine-grained visual cues that are more critical for human appearance modeling.

Across all evaluated deduplication strategies, the results show that substantial redundancy can be removed from the dataset without degrading downstream performance. In several cases, such as moderate L2 and FAISS-based deduplication thresholds, model accuracy is preserved or even slightly improved, despite a reduction of up to 10–15% in the number of training images. More aggressive deduplication settings lead to larger dataset reductions but are accompanied by a gradual performance decline, indicating a clear trade-off between storage efficiency and information retention.

Regarding image compression, the results indicate that moderate JPEG compression (quality 85–100) has a negligible impact on detection and segmentation performance, with mAP50 and IoU variations typically below 1%. Even under more aggressive compression (JPEG 65), performance degradation remains limited, confirming the robustness of both YOLO11 and SegFormer to moderate information loss. Notably, car detection and segmentation are consistently less sensitive to compression artifacts than person-related tasks, likely due to the more regular structure and lower texture dependency of vehicle appearances. Overall, these findings demonstrate that controlled deduplication and compression can substantially reduce storage requirements while maintaining high perception performance, supporting their use in scalable and privacy-aware data management pipelines.

To further investigate the computational implications of our preprocessing pipeline, we evaluated the impact of image compression and deduplication on model latency during both training and inference. Deduplication influences only

the composition of the training dataset, by reducing the number of images without altering the content of individual samples. Consequently, it may shorten the overall training duration but does not affect the per-frame processing time. Similarly, compression modifies only the visual quality of the images while preserving their dimensions and structure, and thus should not influence the computational load per frame. To validate these assumptions, we performed multiple experiments comparing compressed and non-compressed datasets, measuring the average time required for inference, loss computation, and post-processing. The results confirmed our expectations, showing negligible differences across all configurations, with a standard deviation of approximately 0.1 ms.

V. DISCUSSION

The evaluation of the proposed pipeline directly addresses the integration of sustainability principles into autonomous vehicle data workflows (RQ1). By applying best practices such as deduplication, anonymization, and compression, we demonstrate how existing techniques can be combined to minimize redundant data, reduce storage needs, and promote responsible data handling. For example, deduplication yielded unique image ratios of 35–75% (CERTH) and 55–95% (iseAuto), indicating the potential for substantial storage and transmission savings.

While we do not measure energy consumption, carbon emissions, or latency directly, we use storage volume reduction as a practical proxy. We argue that reducing stored and transmitted data indirectly contributes to energy efficiency and reduced computational demand. We acknowledge, however, that this is an indirect measure and cannot substitute for hardware-level sustainability metrics, which would require controlled benchmarking on specific platforms.

In response to RQ2, the pipeline's design emphasizes scalability and modularity, allowing deployment across diverse sensor configurations and operational environments. The structured post-processing framework includes anonymization steps with high accuracy rates—over 90% for CERTH and 99% for iseAuto—ensuring privacy compliance without sacrificing data utility. The pipeline's modular nature supports integration into federated data ecosystems, such as data spaces, promoting standardized data sharing and interoperability.

Addressing RQ3, the structured post-processing pipeline enhances dataset quality, privacy compliance, and storage efficiency. The compression ratios achieved—50% for CERTH and 70% for iseAuto—highlight the effectiveness of embedded edge processing in reducing environmental impact. These reductions indirectly translate into lower power consumption and transmission requirements, aligning with the goals of sustainable AI development. At the same time, task-level validation using YOLO and Segformer semantic segmentation on processed data indicates that key functional performance is preserved.

TABLE 9. Ablation study for YOLO11 and SegFormer semantic segmentation.

Component used				YOLO11		SegFormer	
Deduplication	Anonymization	Number of images	Compression	Person $mAP50 \uparrow$	Car $mAP50 \uparrow$	Person $IoU \uparrow$	Car $IoU \uparrow$
\times	\times	2160	PNG	86.47%	90.22%	67.27%	80.28%
		2160	JPEG 100	85.37%	89.85%	69.14%	78.87%
		2160	JPEG 85	86.59%	90.11%	68.90%	79.74%
		2160	JPEG 65	86.14%	89.55%	70.37%	78.35
\times	\checkmark	2160	PNG	85.02%	89.74%	68.04%	80.84%
		2160	JPEG 100	85.27%	91.14%	68.88%	80.52%
		2160	JPEG 85	83.92%	89.81%	68.74%	78.97%
		2160	JPEG 65	84.82%	89.39%	69.60%	80.70%
L2, $\tau = 2.0$	\times	2068	PNG	87.65%	89.28%	69.17%	78.88
		2083	JPEG 100	87.01%	89.32%	70.66%	78.57%
		2085	JPEG 85	86.09%	89.42%	69.11%	80.25%
		2092	JPEG 65	86.12%	89.31%	69.05%	79.90%
L2, $\tau = 2.5$	\times	1996	PNG	84.49%	89.31%	69.31%	80.58%
		2003	JPEG 100	84.44%	90.16%	68.53%	79.71%
		2007	JPEG 85	86.16%	88.90%	69.49%	79.98%
		2007	JPEG 65	85.89%	88.68%	69.24%	79.56%
L2, $\tau = 3.0$	\times	1856	PNG	85.73%	88.90%	68.75%	80.11%
		1865	JPEG 100	84.26%	88.76%	67.50%	79.66%
		1883	JPEG 85	85.62%	89.01%	69.24%	79.65%
		1881	JPEG 65	85.75%	89.05%	69.52%	79.64%
CS, $\tau = 0.85$	\times	766	PNG	79.27%	87.42%	66.69%	79.10%
		755	JPEG 100	79.32%	85.10%	68.31%	78.36%
		757	JPEG 85	74.38%	86.19%	69.28%	78.38%
		753	JPEG 65	78.09%	85.95%	67.25%	79.04%
CS, $\tau = 0.90$	\times	1160	PNG	81.57%	88.07%	68.16%	80.20%
		1168	JPEG 100	82.01%	88.24%	69.72%	79.34%
		1170	JPEG 85	80.41%	87.14%	68.61%	78.78%
		1165	JPEG 65	79.35%	88.39%	69.50%	79.62%
CS, $\tau = 0.95$	\times	1745	PNG	86.05%	89.60%	69.62%	79.33%
		1748	JPEG 100	86.68%	91.04%	68.91%	80.63%
		1764	JPEG 85	84.35%	88.68%	67.55%	79.82%
		1771	JPEG 65	85.19%	90.29%	69.29%	81.29%
FAISS, $\tau = 2.0^2$	\times	2044	PNG	83.65%	89.64%	68.54%	80.19%
		2044	JPEG 100	84.77%	89.46%	68.90%	79.65%
		2047	JPEG 85	84.86%	89.13%	69.38%	78.55%
		2061	JPEG 65	84.66%	89.79%	68.76%	79.74%
FAISS, $\tau = 2.5^2$	\times	1938	PNG	86.09%	89.38%	69.65%	80.44%
		1930	JPEG 100	84.69%	90.37%	69.78%	79.83%
		1937	JPEG 85	85.93%	90.13%	69.45%	81.03%
		1942	JPEG 65	84.14%	89.54%	69.00%	79.47%
FAISS, $\tau = 3.0^2$	\times	1755	PNG	84.36%	90.00%	68.41%	79.19%
		1755	JPEG 100	82.97%	90.28%	68.23%	79.14%
		1764	JPEG 85	86.06%	89.75%	69.96%	78.92%
		1770	JPEG 65	84.43%	89.71%	70.61%	80.43%

As a summary, the proposed pipeline achieves storage reductions of up to 70.9%, anonymization accuracy exceeding 99%, and deduplication ratios ranging between 35–95%, all while maintaining comparable performance of AI tasks ($mAP50 \geq 75\%$ for YOLO, $IoU \sim 70\%$ for SegFormer). A current limitation lies in the empirical tuning of parameters such as the similarity threshold τ , which, while effective, may require adaptation for different datasets or sensor configurations.

A. LIMITATIONS

While each module contributes to the overall objectives, there are inherent trade-offs and limitations. First of all, both the image deduplication and anonymization methods rely on predefined thresholds, which directly affect the efficiency and the sensitivity of the proposed components. These manually tuned thresholds are dataset-dependent and may not generalize across scenarios. Specifically, for the deduplication process, the threshold τ was empirically

tuned to achieve an effective trade-off between redundancy reduction and scene diversity. For example, values in the range of τ between 0.9 and 0.95 for cosine similarity or τ between 2.0 and 2.5 for Euclidean distance achieved balanced outcomes in our evaluation. Overall, overly aggressive filtering may remove frames containing subtle but important details, especially in low-motion scenes, risking semantic data loss due to misconfigured thresholds. Regarding the anonymization module, improper threshold selection can lead to false negatives, which may expose sensitive information, while false positives risk obscuring relevant image content.

For compression, reliance on lossless techniques ensures preservation of exact, fine-grained data details, which is critical for accuracy-sensitive tasks. However, this approach often results in lower compression ratios and may limit the ability to exploit lossy or task-specific compression methods that could optimize data for downstream tasks requiring rich, enhanced feature representations. Achieving the ideal balance between data fidelity and storage efficiency requires extensive tuning of compression parameters, which is challenging because optimal settings vary depending on the dataset characteristics, sensor modalities, and requirements of downstream tasks.

These limitations highlight the importance of context-aware tuning and task-specific evaluation when applying the proposed pipeline.

Another critical limitation of the current pipeline is the absence of hardware constraint analysis for edge device deployment, which is essential for enabling onboard execution prior to data transfer to centralized, high-processing data centers. Edge platforms in autonomous vehicles operate under stringent constraints including limited processing power, restricted memory bandwidth, strict power budgets, and challenging thermal conditions. The pipeline's reliance on deep learning models creates a substantial dependency on GPU-intensive hardware, which can generate significant heat and drain power resources during intensive computations. Although lightweight models were selected and validated on general-purpose hardware, the lack of empirical benchmarking on actual embedded automotive platforms means that potential quality degradation, processing latency, and energy consumption under real-world edge constraints remain unquantified.

Finally, while the pipeline enables centralized data aggregation from vehicle fleets, its real-world scalability presents open challenges. Deployment at fleet scale would require robust scheduling mechanisms, real-time synchronization, and governance frameworks to ensure consistency, traceability, and compliance across distributed systems.

These limitations reflect the applied, proof-of-concept nature of the study. We view this work as a foundational step toward scalable, sustainable, and privacy-aware data workflows in autonomous vehicle systems. Overall, our implementation serves as a practical reference for post hoc data optimization in AV systems. While effective in its current form, further validation is needed across broader

tasks, hardware environments, and deployment scales to fully realize its potential.

B. FUTURE WORK

Despite its practical value, the proposed pipeline with the above-mentioned limitations warrant further consideration and analysis for the future deployment of such solutions. The limitation of manually-tuned thresholds, which makes the proposed pipeline sensitive to dataset changes, could be highly improved through automated or adaptive tuning strategies, in order improve robustness and reduce deployment friction. In principle, this could be achieved through adaptive or clustering-based strategies; however, such approaches are highly sensitive to variations in sensor resolution, environmental dynamics, and motion characteristics, which hinder generalization across datasets. Therefore, a controlled empirical tuning remains the most robust and interpretable choice for the present framework, however this field could highly benefit from future research.

Second, the pipeline is currently validated on general-purpose hardware. Although designed with edge execution in mind, it requires comprehensive profiling on representative edge hardware, along with exploration of optimization strategies such as model quantization, pruning, hardware acceleration mapping, and dynamic workload distribution between edge and cloud resources. Future work should benchmark the pipeline on edge devices to quantify latency, throughput, and power consumption. Finally, for point-cloud data future work includes exploring alternative compression techniques, such as MPEG compression [60] or Google Draco [61], to further enhance storage efficiency.

VI. CONCLUSION

This work presents an applied study focused on the integration and evaluation of existing data handling techniques to support sustainable data collection in autonomous vehicle systems. Rather than proposing novel algorithms, the contribution lies in assembling a modular and scalable data pipeline that incorporates proven practices—such as image deduplication, event-based filtering, anonymization, and compression—into a cohesive workflow tailored for autonomous driving scenarios.

By embedding these components into a unified system, the pipeline significantly reduces data volume while preserving the integrity and utility of critical information. More specifically, image deduplication achieved a unique image ratio ranging from 35% to 75%, and up to 95% for the iseAuto dataset, indicating substantial potential for reducing redundant data. Furthermore, the compression techniques reduced storage requirements by 50% for CERTH and 70% for iseAuto, significantly lowering data volume without compromising information integrity. Experimental validation on two real-world datasets confirms its effectiveness, demonstrating substantial gains in storage efficiency and privacy compliance exceeding 90% for CERTH and

reaching 99% for iseAuto, while maintaining performance on AI tasks. This approach aligns with broader national and international sustainability goals, including climate neutrality targets, and provides a practical foundation for greener AI development in mobility systems. Ultimately, this integrated pipeline supports broader national and international goals for climate-neutral and efficient AI systems in mobility, and may serve as a reference implementation for similar applied deployments across the intelligent transportation domain.

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KOSMAS TSIAKAS received the Diploma degree in electrical and computer engineering from the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH), Greece, in 2019. He is currently pursuing the Ph.D. degree in robotics with the Department of Production and Management Engineering, Engineering School, Democritus University of Thrace. He is a Research Associate at the Information Technologies Institute, Centre of Research and Technology Hellas, and contributes to various EU and nationally funded research projects. His research interests include the fields of robotic perception and navigation, AI, and autonomous driving.

MAURO BELLONE (Member, IEEE) received the M.S. degree in automation engineering and the Ph.D. degree in mechanical and industrial engineering from the University of Salento, Lecce, Italy, in 2014. From 2015 to 2020, he was with the Applied Artificial Intelligence Research Group, Chalmers University of Technology. Since 2021, he has been an Adjunct Professor at the Tallinn University of Technology, supporting the Research Team in the area of smart transportation systems. Currently, he is an Associate Professor with Universitas Mercatorum, Italy. His research interests include the area of advanced sensory perception for mobile robotics and artificial intelligence.

IOANNIS MARIOLIS received the Diploma and Ph.D. degrees in electrical and computer engineering from the University of Patras (UoP), Greece, in 2002 and 2009, respectively. During his Ph.D. studies, he was a Teaching and Research Assistant at the Wire Communications Laboratory, Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering. From 2010 to 2011, he was a Research Assistant at the Medical Physics Laboratory, School of Medicine, UoP. From March 2010 to March 2011, he was an Adjunct Lecturer at the Department of Informatics and Means of Mass Communication, Technological Educational Institute of Patras, Greece. Since February 2012, he has been at the Information Technologies Institute (ITI) as a Postdoctoral Research Fellow. His research interests include statistical signal processing, machine vision, medical image analysis, and pattern recognition.

ANTONIOS GASTERATOS (Senior Member, IEEE) received the M.Eng. and Ph.D. degrees from the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Democritus University of Thrace (DUTH), Xanthi, Greece, in 1994 and 1998, respectively. From 1999 to 2000, he was a Visiting Researcher with the Laboratory of Integrated Advanced Robotics (LIRALab), DIST, University of Genoa, Genoa, Italy. He is currently a Professor and the Head of the Production and Management Engineering Department, DUTH. He is also the Director of the Laboratory of Robotics and Automation, DUTH, and teaches courses in robotics, automatic control systems, electronics, mechatronics, and computer vision. He has authored over 220 papers in books, journals, and conferences. His research interests include mechatronics and robot vision. He is a fellow of IET. He has served as a reviewer for several scientific journals and international conferences. He has organized/co-organized several international conferences. He is a Subject Editor of *Electronics Letters* and an Associate Editor of *International Journal of Optomecatronics*. More details about him are available at: <http://robotics.pme.duth.gr/antonis>

DIMITRIOS GIAKOUKIS has been working as a Researcher with the Information Technologies Institute (ITI), since February 2007, where he is currently a Principal Researcher (Grade B') at the Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH). He has been involved in more than 20 research projects, funded by the EC and the Greek State. These include the Horizon 2020 RAMCIP, BADGER, HR-Recycler, Ageing@work, and BACCHUS projects, where he contributed to the technical coordination and quality management of the project consortium. In addition, he has been the Technical Coordinator of Project "ACTIVE" in Healthcare Service Robots, funded by the Hellenic Foundation of Research and Innovation (HFRI), and a PI of CERTH for the Project ARISE (Horizon Europe). He is the Coordinator of the EC-Funded projects RobetArme, MANiBOT, and PLIADES (Horizon Europe), in the fields of AI, data, and robotics. His research interests include human-robot interaction, robot vision, service robot perception and cognition, affective computing, human motion, activity and behavior analysis and modeling, safe and social-aware robot navigation, bio-signals processing and sensor management, multimodal interfaces, machine learning, and pattern recognition.

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DIMITRIOS TZOVARAS (Senior Member, IEEE) received the Diploma and Ph.D. degrees in electrical and computer engineering from the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece, in 1992 and 1997, respectively. He is currently the Director of the Information Technologies Institute, Centre for Research and Technology Hellas, Thessaloniki. His research interests include visual analytics, 3-D object recognition, search and retrieval, behavioral biometrics, assistive technologies, information and knowledge management, computer graphics, and virtual reality.